

FACTORS FOR INCREASING THE STABILITY OF GRAIN PRODUCTION AND PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

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(Abstract)

The role and importance of the agricultural sector in ensuring the food security of the population on a global scale is increasing every day. In particular, wheat is one of the most common cereal crops. Wheat bread is highly valued for its taste, satiety and digestibility, the use of resources and opportunities available in our country to ensure a guaranteed supply of agricultural products to the population, further increase productivity and interest in the introduction of scientific achievements and modern approaches in the field is an urgent problem.

(Key words): grain and grain products, grain production, productivity, efficiency, grain independence, agricultural technology.

Introduction (Introduction)

In the Action Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, "...introduce intensive methods in the field of agricultural production, first of all, create new breeding varieties of crops adapted to local soil, climatic and environmental conditions. Particular attention was paid to the introduction of modern agricultural technologies in the fields, especially the development of grain production"[1]. According to international statistics, the total volume of wheat products produced in the countries of the world is 772 million tons. The top ten wheat producing countries include the following countries: China, India, Russia, USA, France, Canada, Pakistan, Ukraine, Australia and Germany. Grain yields exceeded 55 q/ha, and the total yield was 6.5 q/ha. -7.8 million tons.

(Research Methodology)

The study of existing scientific research on ensuring the stability of grain production, comparative comparison of tariff pricing, the study of statistical data and economic comparison and analysis, logical thinking, scientific abstraction, information grouping, the growth of average production volumes of products are harmonious for wave methods, are widely used.

It can also be seen that a number of economists have considered this concept in connection with other economic categories. According to B. Mamarakhimov, it is desirable to ensure the food security of the region mainly

through the development of agricultural production and domestic markets, partly through the import of food products from abroad. However, the Strategy for Agricultural Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 states that the average yield of row crops will increase to 70 t/ha by 2025 and to 75 t/ha by 2030[2]. In this regard, application of intensive agricultural technologies in cultivation of winter wheat varieties with high productivity, efficient use of irrigated lands along with increase of grain yield, improvement of technological indicators of grain quality are the most relevant. In irrigated conditions each province has different soil and climatic conditions depending on its geographical location and regions. At the same time, a set of new agro-technological measures used to obtain new promising varieties will be developed based on the natural conditions of the area and recommended for use by grain growers in the near future. Therefore, we will abolish the state order for cotton and grain production and gradually move to a system of purchasing these products on market principles.

If we do not go down this road, our farmers and peasants will not have the freedom to grow produce, they will not get the expected benefits, and the style of the governors will not change.

- reformed the state support fund for agriculture and noted that it would be possible to allocate cheap loans to other sectors of the agricultural sector. [3,4].

(Analysis and results)

The existence of multilateral linkages between grain production and sectors of the economy allows us to emphasize that sustainable grain production is the basis for ensuring the stability of all agricultural production and the commodity market. Sustainable grain production has significant potential for the development of a large part of the country's economic system [5,6]. At the same time, considering the issues of defining scientific category "Sustainability of grain production", peculiarities of structure of production-economic potential of grain production, cycles of economic development of grain production, influence of changing weather and climate conditions released Development of climatic conditions and long-term scenarios of ensuring sustainability of grain production remain understudied. At the same time, rapidly changing economic and technological conditions of agriculture, instability of grain growing require yes. Economic growth in the grain industry is represented by growth in gross output of grain, both in volume and per capita, which is stable in dynamics[7,8].

Given the unique characteristics of the industry, the growth of this indicator should be a trend and not the only dominant indicator of productivity growth due to favourable conditions.

Today, our republic will produce a total of 2,550,000 tonnes of wheat in the 2022 crop, averaging 2.5 tonnes per hectare of irrigated area.

- A total of 1,783,500 tonnes of marketable wheat as a state resource and 266,500 tonnes for seed will be purchased from the State Agricultural Support Fund;

- 500,000 tonnes will be accepted by farms and other grain producers for temporary storage from the Fund's commercial representative for subsequent sale on the exchanges.[9]

Wheat from the 2022 crop received from wheat producers for temporary storage at the trade representative will be sold through the exchange in July-August 2022. Grain products are divided into 2 types:

1. Cereals (wheat, barley, oats, rice)
2. Millet (oats, maize, beans, etc.) [10]

TABLE 1: Cereal and legume crops cultivated on farms of all categories in the Republic of Uzbekistan[1]

Type of products	Unit of measurement	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Cereals and legumes, total	thousand tons	7 288,5	6 535,5	7 437,8	7 636,0	7 634,6
including:	x	x	x	x	x	x
Wheat	thousand tons	6 079,2	5 410,8	6 093,5	6 157,8	5 984,8
Barley	thousand tons	134,3	111,8	133,5	161,5	95,8
Rye	thousand tons	-	0,7	0,8	5,2	3,8
Corn for grain	thousand tons	389,4	413,2	421,3	475,3	590,0
Corghum	thousand tons	-	21,1	14,7	19,0	22,1
Millet	thousand tons	-	54,5	104,3	99,1	99,8

Oats	thousand tons	-	1,3	1,7	1,9	53,7
Buckwheat	thousand tons	-	0,1	0,6	0,02	0,2
Rice	thousand tons	395,4	221,1	314,7	293,5	334,2
Leguminous crops, total	thousand tons	212,5	260,0	339,6	401,6	439,8
including:	x	x	x	x	x	x
Peas	thousand tons	-	37,5	34,2	23,9	29,7
Beans	thousand tons	-	65,1	72,2	77,3	73,7
Lentils	thousand tons	-	-	2,1	0,01	0,2

[1]_Compiled by the author on the basis of information from STAT.uz.

It would also be no exaggeration to say that our neighbouring Republic of Kazakhstan has found its place in Central Asia, as well as in the world market, in sowing and selling grain products. We know that Kazakhstan is a neighboring country to us, but why have we not heard of the brand Uzbek wheat or Uzbek grain today? Because farmers themselves have the right to plant and sell their grain when planting and purchasing grain, delivery of grain products is important.

In this regard, in order to provide the population with wheat and flour products in 2022 in the republic planted 1 million 27 thousand hectares of land with wheat. This figure exceeds last year's by 1 million tonnes. If we take the parameters of the harmonic wave of wheat production in these years (Figure 1),

at an interval of five years of wheat, we can see that the efficiency of production

is increasing .

[2].Compiled by the author on the basis of information from [STAT.uz](https://stat.uz).

Figure 1: Parameters of harmonic wave of wheat production in agricultural holdings of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2000-2022 (thousand tons)

The periods of economic development of grain production have been determined, characteristics and duration of corresponding growth and decline phases have been indicated, and parameters of harmonic wave of grain production have been determined.

Conclusion & Recommendations

Grain is one of the most common cereal crops. The multifaceted linkages between cereal production and economic sectors underline that sustainable cereal production is the basis for ensuring the stability of all agricultural production and the commodity market. Sustainable grain production has significant potential for the development of a large part of a country's economic system. More than half of the world's population uses wheat bread for food. Wheat bread is high in protein and starch, and since protein substances are mainly found in gluten, it is used to bake quality bread.

What should be done for this?

- expanding the list of goods for sale,
- it is necessary to introduce new trading tools that ensure the dynamics of stock trading.

Of course, there should also be adequate supply for this purpose:

I can make the following additional suggestions to ensure the sustainability of grain production.

- increasing the number of mills,
- expanding the area of grain cultivation and increasing its productivity,

-introducing a system for covering the transportation costs for the delivery of flour and flour products to remote villages,
-as well as flour and flour from other regions of the country and abroad it is necessary to prevent shortages in the market by importing products,
-to ensure price stability.

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